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A crude Earth ephemeris for TYCHO astrometry

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The following routine calculates the barycentric position of the Earth with a maximum error of about 0.4 %. This is sufficient e.g. for calculating the parallax factors for TYCHO astrometry.

Note that a different routine (earth) is available when full accuracy is needed, e.g. for the calculation of stellar aberration.

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C*****
C      SUBROUTINE cearth(t, b)
C*****
C
C  HIPPARCOS - NDAC - General routines - Crude Earth ephemeris
C
C  INPUT:      t      = time since J1988.0                [s]
C
C  OUTPUT:     b(1:3) = barycentric position of Earth    [m]
C
C  NOTE:       Both arguments are Double Precision (REAL*8)
C
C  ACCURACY:   For t between .0D+00 and 1.58D+08 (1988.0 to 1993.0)
C              the maximum positional error is 5.9D+08 m = 0.0040 AU.
C              The rms positional error is 3.6D+08 m = 0.0024 AU.
C
C  L Lindegren 1987 Oct 6
C
C      IMPLICIT DOUBLE PRECISION (a-h,o-z)
C      DIMENSION b(3), c(3,3)
C      PARAMETER (omega = 0.0172021240D+00/86400D+00,
C                e = 0.016714D+00, g0 = -0.04128D+00)
C      DATA c/ .540817D+09, -.334118D+11, -.145868D+12,
C              -.202315D+10, .133781D+12, -.306652D+11,
C              -.883589D+09, .580048D+11, -.132951D+11 /
C      arg = omega*t + g0
C      arg = arg + e*dsin(arg)
C      co = dcos(arg)
C      si = dsin(arg)
C      DO 10 i = 1, 3
C          b(i) = c(1,i) + c(2,i)*co + c(3,i)*si
10 CONTINUE
RETURN
END

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